

ABSTRACT

This study was carried out with the method of document review by scanning how and under which conditions funding was provided to private schools in some countries at international level, and private school funding support suggestions that can be applied in our country. This method includes the analysis of written and verbal materials that contain information about the topics planned to be investigated. Document review involves the analysis of written materials that are targeted to be investigated and contain information about the event (s) (Şimşek, 2009, s.40). In this context, private school financing models in the USA, England, France, China and Japan on private school financing and the examples of Georgia and Qatar who are trying to implement reform applications to finance private schools were examined. When the private school financing supports are analyzed by countries, it is seen that the most privilege is in France and the least privilege is in China. In addition, it was observed that in the context of England, the religious foundations provided more privilege and support to private schools of different kinds than the other countries. When financial support is examined, Japan comes to the fore in terms of fiscal discipline and control.

INTRODUCTION

Economics is directly effective in education as in many other fields. Economics "examines the preferences of people and societies in using scarce production resources." (Kumbaracıbaşı, Soral, 1981, p. 13).

Education is "the process of creating the desired behavioral change in the individual through his own life and deliberate acculturation." (Demirel, 2005, p.6). Education and economics have transformed by interacting in their historical processes. Indeed, in the history of civilization, all knowledge continuity has been ensured by transferring or teaching the knowledge from one generation to another through family or non-family persons or different social organizations. Thus, the learning and teaching process evolved with the production process, regardless of the nature of the production and distribution activity.

While education investments are always a priority area for countries in the international arena, the function, status and importance of private schools in education systems vary by country and time. Many countries provide funding support to private schools in order to reach students and ensure that students reach certain standards academically. In this context, countries finance schools with different funding models for private schools (Kurul Tural 2019, p.17).

It is quite new that the relationship between education and employment is the subject of economic analysis. In the literature before Adam Smith (1723-1790), the word education is rarely encountered (Serin, 1979, p. 6). Smith stated that education can be seen as an investment in future earning capacity,

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but there were no studies on the relationship between the quality of the labor force and production at that time (Mc Nabb, 1987, p.157). It is seen that the relations between education and economy have been studied scientifically since the 1950s.

Looking at the 1990s and today, education-employment relations, globalization, increasing global competition, flexible organization and specialization, highly skilled workforce, labor unskilled labor, division and polarization of the labor force, intensification of inequalities, especially between northern and southern countries, within the framework of the concepts of global division have been discussed. In education and employment relations, manpower qualities that exceed national economic needs and required by globalization are discussed and the economic value of education is tried to be drawn in this context (Kurul Tural 2019, p.22).

Cohn and Geske (1989, p.7) determine the financing of education, one of the subject areas of education economics, as follows. Financing for education: Who should pay for the cost of education? To what extent should the state support public and private education in various types and levels of education? How should public support for education be distributed among different levels of government (federal, state and local levels, or central and local governments)? How much of the education cost should be covered by the taxpayer and how much by the direct beneficiaries of the education? Education finance seeks answers to such questions and constitutes one of the fields of study of the education economy.

According to Levin (1987s.426) the education funding constitutes one of the important subject areas of education economy. Apart from obtaining financial resources corresponding to the real resources required for the provision of various types and levels of education; education funding also examines the process of distributing these resources among different regions, provinces, education types and levels, individuals and groups from different social and economic backgrounds.

METHOD OF THE RESEARCH

This research was conducted with a qualitative research approach in accordance with its purpose. Qualitative research approach is based on looking at the research object in a holistic way and examining it within its context (Punch, 2005). When conducting qualitative research, the main purpose is to identify and establish a link between these issues (Patton, 2002).

This study was conducted with the method of document analysis by scanning national and international documents, how and under what conditions fund support is provided to private schools in some countries at the international level, the effects of the US charter system, which is widely known among these funding, on the education system of different countries, and private school financing support proposals that can be applied in our country. This method includes the analysis of written and oral materials that contain information about the topics to be researched. Document review covers the analysis of written materials containing information about the event or facts that are aimed to be investigated (Şimşek, 2009, p. 40). In this context, private school financing models in the USA, England, France, China and Japan on private school financing and the examples of Georgia and Qatar trying to implement reform applications to finance private schools were examined.

PRIVATE SCHOOL FINANCING MODELS - INTERNATIONAL EXAMPLES

This section contains information about private school funding models of some countries.

People's Republic of China: Private Schools and Funding Models

The first private schools in the Republic of China have been operating since 1911. Private schools in China were also run by the city council (Kouzhu, 2008, p.548). After the revolution of the People's Republic of China in 1949, private schools continued their activities until today.

Indirect Management Model and Financial Functioning of Private Schools

The Shanghai Municipal Education Bureau adopted the indirect management model in private schools and provided funding. Shanghai Republican education governing bodies adopted the Indirect Management Administrative Model approach to the problem of managing private schools, unlike the administration of municipal schools. The basic spirit of the system is as follows: Board of directors and

principals complete the authority to take responsibility for the practical work of schools; educational administration has established rules, examined and applied more serious issues.

Dual authority: The municipality is an important precondition and environment for educational administration indirect management of private schools. The dual authority model of the administrative management of private schools refers to different categories of authority, divided management between principals and governing boards. The governing boards were responsible for all operations of the schools and appointment of the principal. The principal had authority to run school affairs. The Shanghai Special Municipal Elementary and Secondary Schools Regulations decided that the founders of private schools would elect directors to form a board with full responsibility for the running of the school. The principal was responsible to the board of directors and was managing the business of the school" (Kouzhu, 2008, p.549).

In principle, the powers of the executive boards of private schools are:

- Supervises school financing, financing planning, controlling the budget and accounting, renovation and maintenance of the school, financial matters and other financial affairs.
- Appoints the principal regarding the school administration.

School governing boards should list the financial status of the school, important issues, income and expenditure items, together with amounts within one month after the end of the fiscal year. They are obliged to submit the report containing these lists to the education administrative bodies of the city.

Enrollment management: The establishment of qualification standards and the enforcement of enrollment have had a profound effect in the enrollment administration of private schools. The qualification standards for private schools in Shanghai's Republic period mainly included items such as wages, equipment, teachers, principals, and teaching administration. The following 3 basic criteria are required in private school qualifications.

- Schools had to have established assets or funds. In addition, they had other income that could keep the school running. Even without any established assets or funds, they must have other income that can maintain annual fees.
- School area, school building, playground, school furniture, teaching aids, etc. it should have some basic facilities.
- All teachers and administrators must be qualified for training. Managers must speak Chinese. Full-time teachers must exceed 2/3. In addition to applying for registration, private schools must attach the following items in detail to the instruction booklet.

These items include the name of the school (foreign name should be listed if any), type of school, school location, school area and school status, school evolution, source funds, study budget and incidental budget list, organizational curriculum and all kinds of rules, books, equipment, examples, schools. Furniture and sports and hygiene facilities, a leading list of teachers, a table linked to all students, an alumni list, etc. Only private schools can be allowed to enroll in accordance with all the above-mentioned rules.

Economic Interventions in Private Schools

Each school must determine the student's full tuition waiver and incidental expenses. The percentage of full tuition waiver in private primary schools should not be less than 20%; Secondary school fee waiver rate should not be less than 15%. At the end of each month, each school term and each year, the committee is required to hold a meeting to check the status of income and expenditure within a specified period, and to carry out partial control over all kinds of school goods and equipment. When this meeting is held, the staff responsible for funds are asked to explain. The monthly bank statement must be checked and sealed by the members of the Expense Audit Committee. Any income and expenses should not be misused; the determined tax should be handled according to the types of wages and the rules to ensure teachers' behavior (Kouzhu, 2008, p. 563).

United Kingdom: Private Schools and Funding Models in Britain

These schools are considered to be independent in Britain. This is because they do not benefit from any financial support or other support from the local or central government (Walford, 2003, p.154).

Private (Independent) Schools and their Financial Operations

Most independent schools in the UK still benefit significantly from their charitable status. In order for a charity to be exempt from many taxes, it must have acquired charity status according to the Charities Act of 1993 (Palfreyman, 2003, p. 142). Various private school associations have tried to successfully replace this term with the term 'independent' in order to avoid the effects of its particular meaning on elitism and privilege. For this reason, independent school expression was used instead of private in the studies (Walford, 2003, p. 160).

Charities - Education Taxes

Income Tax: Charities are exempt from income tax provided that income is used only for charitable purposes. Revenues; It includes rent, interest and dividends from land and property, income from certain fundraising activities, and income from a charitable trading activity (eg school catering).

Corporate Tax: Aid association provides exemption from corporate tax as well as income tax. This exemption applies where the school is operated as a charity.

Capital Gain Tax: It grants exemption to charities from capital gains tax.

VAT: Under the education value added tax law, there is an obligation to tax on inputs (purchases made to provide their services). Outputs - goods and services that help provide education for sales (registration fee to students, sale of meals, stationery, school trips) are exempt from VAT.

Stamp Tax: Finance law grants exemption from stamp tax to charities.

Rates: The Local Authorities Finance Law provides an 80 percent rating discount for charities. This tax concession probably has the most benefits for independent schools, after the VAT exemption.

Donations and Inheritances: Donations made to charities are exempt from income tax. Inheritance left to charities is exempt from inheritance tax due to the ownership of the deceased.

Financial Advantages of Charities and Possible Implications

Charities are exempt from inheritance tax on the sum of internal income on any donation and inheritance added to the donation. Profits donated by the company to the charity through the school's trading company are also not taxed. Another advantage is that it does not have to collect 17.5% VAT on the annual tuition fee (Palfreyman, 2003, p.145).

Outcomes for Private and Public School Students

It is also noted that private schools, unlike most public schools, some research has determined the role of providing better resources to shape student outcomes in the private sector. Graddy and Stevens (2005, p. 440) state that lower proportion of talented students is an important determinant of tuition in private schools and can determine the larger resource effects in their schools. In the examination of private schools in England, student-teacher ratios of schools with low success actually give better examination results (Machin & Wilson, 2009, p. 220).

Public-Private Initiatives - City Academies

In education in the UK, there are two main forms of private sector participation in the public sector:

- **Private finance initiatives:** Covers all non-academic initiatives such as the construction, renovation, heating systems, catering services of school buildings.
- **Public-private partnerships:** It includes studies to increase academic achievement and educational qualifications.

City Academies Program

City academies are new independent public schools established on the basis of partnership or joint venture between central government and private sector sponsors. The academy program has been applied to urban schools with low academic achievement (schools serving students over 11 and 12 years old) at the secondary education level. Annual income financing is comparable to other public schools. No fees are paid by the parents. Private sector sponsors can be from various fields (business, belief groups, individuals). The sponsors hand over the school to the board of directors, which is largely made up of appointed people. Compared to public schools run by the Local Education Authorities (LEA), 'academies leading boards' employ all academy staff. The board of directors is responsible for regulating wage levels, service conditions, personnel structure, career development, discipline and performance management policies. The academy is expected to specialize in at least one subject area, initially selected at the discretion of the sponsor, but which can be determined by considering local community interests. The most striking distinctions between academies and other public schools are their autonomy, presence of private sector sponsors, and degrees of participation.

Table- 1 -Private Actors in Education and State Finance Productivity

Finance of the initiative			
	State	Private/State	Private(capital)
<u>Service Presentation</u>			
State	The management of state schools	Expert schools ³	
Private	Service agreements	Academies and some LEA services	Private finance initiatives
State and Private	Teacher training (when required)	EducationAct regions ⁴	Service Agreements

Machin & Wilson, 2009, p. 221.

Table-1 shows the participation of public and private sector in the UK in the provision of services and financing of education.

Japan Private School Financial Operations

Considering the Japanese history, it is seen that there are certain isolation periods. These periods can be explained as the Japanese isolation from the outside world in order to absorb the models they bought from outside (Cansu, 2003, p.27). Thanks to these periods, one of the greatest characteristics of Japan, "not discarding the old while buying the new even in the process of change, and adapting the new elements to its own culture as much as possible" is realized (Kayhan, 2009). The most striking aspect of Japan's development is undoubtedly that education is the most prominent development dynamics (Ekinci, 2010, p.33).

Private Schools

Private education plays an important role in the Japanese formal education system. For this purpose, the Private School Law, which was first enacted in 1949 and lastly amended by Law No. 42 dated May 12, 2004, became effective on April 1, 2007, supports the development of private (independent)

³Expert schools are secondary schools that follow the National Curriculum and specialize in a specified area. While small amounts of funding must be provided through private sector sponsors, the majority of funding comes in the form of more government support than that provided by specialist public schools.

⁴ Education Action Zones include a cluster of about 15 to 25 schools that adopt innovative practices to raise educational standards in disadvantaged areas. They receive around £1 million in additional funding for this (about 75% from the central government and 25% from private sector sponsors).

schools for the benefit of the public. The Ministry of Education, Culture, Sports, Science and Technology (MEXT) places the promotion of private schools as an important policy issue.

Generally, private schools are supported by their own tuition fees. Under the Private School Promotion Incentive Act, the government provides support to private institutions for current and other expenditures. In fiscal 2007, MEXT (2007) donated 8.6 percent of its total budget to private schools. An aid grant of 103.9 billion yen has been provided to cover current expenditure in private schools. It allocated 22.7 billion yen in administrative expenses for private school facilities. Low-interest long-term loans are also provided for private institutions through the Japan Private Schools Promotion and Mutual Aid Agency. Schools can use funds to develop their own facilities and equipment (IBE, 2006).

Private schools are under the authority of the governorship, not the municipalities. Governorates have the authority to approve the establishment and abolition of private schools, to ask schools to submit reports on educational activities, statistics and other necessary issues, and to close them if they violate laws and regulations. However, governorships should seek the opinion of the Special School Council established in each province before specific powers can be exercised. Private institutions are allowed to establish private educational institutions upon meeting the standards set by the supervisory authority and obtaining the approval of the Minister of Education. Teachers are expected to have the same qualifications as teachers in all public schools. Although more diverse classes can be offered in private schools, the course of education should comply with national standards (Nozawa et al. 2011, p.13).

Educational Administration for Private Schools

For school administration in Japan, it is subject to the Japanese Private School Act (JPSL). The articles of law on educational management for private schools are stated below.

- Regarding the administration of private schools, each governorate establishes a private school council to discuss matters subject to its authority in accordance with the Private School Law.
- The private school council is formed with the number of members specified by the governorship. Two members are appointed by the governorship from among those with academic experience in education.
- The term of office of private school council members is four years. However, in the event of a vacancy, two members may be reappointed, provided that the term of an alternate member is the remaining term of the predecessor.
- The Chairman elected by the committee members is appointed by the governor.

School Company

The management activities of private schools in Japan are carried out by school companies. Association, foundation, etc. institutions can also establish and run a school company. Regarding school companies, the management and financing-related items specified in JPSL 2007 are listed below.

- A school company must have the facilities and equipment or funds necessary for the establishment of the private school and the necessary property for the management of the private school.
- Can do a profit-making business to use the profits for the management of private schools, as long as it does not prevent the education of private schools to be established.
- Five or more managers and two or more auditors in the school company as civil servants.
- There is a board of directors that manages the school company. The Executive Board decides on the duties of the school establishment and fulfills the duties of the administrators.
- The duties of the auditor are as follows.

- ✓ Supervises the work of the school company.
- ✓ Checks the condition of the school company's properties.
- ✓ Prepares an audit report for each fiscal year regarding the business or property of the school company and submits it to the Board of Directors and the Board of Trustees within two months from the end of the fiscal year.
- The President represents the school company and directs its activities. Principals (excluding the head) represent the school. Every company has an auditor requirement. Auditors are elected by the president with the approval of the Board of Trustees.
- The auditor must not be a director, councilor or employee of a school company.
- In cases where the interests of the school company and the principal conflict, the principal has no representation power. In this case, a special representative will be appointed by the Board of Trustees at the request of the competent authority or the relevant party or ex officio.
- When the government or local government recognizes that education should be encouraged, it can provide educational institutions with the necessary support for private school education, unless otherwise required by law.
- A time limit is set for the school company if the competent authority believes that the provisions of the law and regulation have been violated, must be disposed of or donated in accordance with the provisions of the law and regulation, or its operation is extremely improper. An order may be given to stop the violation, to improve its operations, or to take other necessary action.
- Before the competent authority attempts to issue an injunction under the provisions of the previous paragraph, the private school council, etc. should listen to their views.

French Private Schools and their Financial Operations

Since private schools in France are tightly regulated, their estimated effects are small, but statistically significant. As France is a country that provides ample public funding to private schools, parents show interest in this system (Bertola, 2015 p.1).

Private School Types

The freedom of education regime in France is one of the basic principles. A significant proportion of the student population is enrolled in private schools at all levels of the French education system, and the overwhelming majority of private schools are covered by the contract introduced by the 1959 Debré Act. In 2011, about 17% of primary school students and about 20% of secondary school students attending private school 2.8% of them were in fully autonomous private schools (as private schools without contracts) such as Montessori institutions (Bertola, 2015, p. 2).

- Non-contractual private institutions (Autonomous schools): Course contents are different from the content of the courses provided by the state.
- Private organizations under a simple contract with the state: Teachers are salaried employees of private law; however, their salary is paid by the state.
- Private organizations covered by a partnership agreement with the state: They are public intermediaries whose teachers are recruited through competitive examination.

It is defined in the Debré law of December 31, 1959, which distinguishes the three types of schools.

Non-Contracted Private Schools

They are primary or secondary schools that do not have an agreement with the state, so these schools are not supported by the Ministry of Education. Tuition fees (from 800 € to 30,000 €) are paid and billed to students' families. These schools do not need to follow the formal curriculum and have great freedoms in teaching methods, but students must master "common basic knowledge" (Hélary, 2020).

Private Schools under Simple Contract with the State

Public and private schools that have contracts with the state coexist within the state system. In exchange for signing a public contract, private schools receive government support, but are regulated and must conform to the national curriculum. The state only issues diplomas in these schools. Exams are held at national level (France Ministry Education National, 2012, p.5).

For private schools the "simple contract" conforms to the principles of public education, but the rules are more flexible. Classrooms must be operational for at least 5 years, and facilities must meet health and safety requirements. The institution should regulate the teaching of basic subjects referring to public education programs. Teachers are appointed by the private authority, they are considered to be employees under private law and are remunerated by the state (European Commission, 2010, p.58).

Private Schools under Government Partnership Agreement

The Debré Act provides financing for the overheads of some charter schools (daily school package: annual support in 2014 was 763 euro for each of the first 80 students) Since the 1977 Germeur Act, teachers' salaries are paid entirely by the state, similar to the salaries of public school teachers. As a condition for state funding, private schools should teach the same curriculum as public schools and only national CAFEP, CAPEPS and CAPLP (Bilgili, 2011, p.103) etc. employ teachers who pass a competition. Private schools can teach a group of students with different teachers, using different materials and teaching methods.

Private school teachers' contracts are not made under private labor law; because the 1992 Coupet-Lang (Verneuil, 2011, p. 57) agreement recognized that private education is a public service. Their employment, such as that of local government employees, is subject to a form of public law (public law contract) that does not administratively restrict job assignments.

United States (USA) Private School Funding Models

The American education system is shaped within the framework of the education program determined by the federal government and state laws that control and regulate this education within the framework of its own laws (Hesapçioğlu & Çelebi, 2011, p. 80). In this context, below is information about private schools in the USA.

Magnet Schools

These are the schools that were opened in the 1960s to eliminate racial discrimination in America. Today, the aim of Magnet School Assistance Program (MSAP) schools is to enable students from different social, economic, ethnic and racial backgrounds to study together and to increase the educational opportunities of students (Policy and Program Studies Service, 2003, p.97).

Financial Functioning of Magnet Schools

Magnet schools, which were previously supported by the Ministry of Education or funds based on anti-racial discrimination, still continue their activities through these funds or with donations from states and regions. However, magnet schools based on art education demand annual fees from students' families (Lohmann, 2004, p. 8). In addition to allocating budgets, some states have made implementations in the law that retired teachers teach at school for one year without losing their retirement salaries (Archer, 2003, p. 26). Magnet schools are financed by more than one official and private person or institution. These aids are provided at different rates for each school (Hesapçioğlu & Çelebi, 2011, p. 92).

Rental - Charter Schools

Charter schools are run by a school-based governing board, rather than being accountable to the local school board. They are exempt from most of the regulations that apply to public schools. For example, they may follow a different curriculum. Teachers may have different salary schemes or professional qualifications than teachers in regular public schools. The role of parents in the decision-making process of schools is significantly higher than that of general public schools (William, 2012, p.276).

According to Kuehn (1995, p. 88), charter schools are seen as the US adaptation of the law on the opening of "donation-based" schools adopted in Britain in 1988. Charter schools can receive education funding for up to three years, but must spend no more than two years for pre-application (U.S Department of Education, 2003).

Table-2 - Comparison of State, Charter and Private Schools

	State	Rental (Charter)	Private
Who can apply	No prerequisites. Several handicaps may exist.	No prerequisites.	Special talents and situations are watched.
The obligations of School	<i>No child left behind yasası</i> Standart teSTS	<i>No child left behind yasası</i> Test included in the school contract	Responsibility to families, not to the state
Efficiency	Obligatory	Obligatory (against specific and limited rules)	Not Obligatory
Cost belonging to the student	Primary School is completely free. Some payments in secondary education for various activities and materials.	Same as the state schools	Enrollment, transport and school installments
Curriculum	Several legal restrictions (religious, sexual and health education).	Some legal restrictions are valid	No restrictions. Religious approaches to academic matters are possible

Utah State Office of Education, 2004.

Table-2 shows the comparison of state, charter and private schools in the USA. Many charter schools are at risk and address students with disabilities (U.S. Department of Education, 2003).

Financial Operation of Charter Schools

There are two different structures of charter schools: schools that are converted from normal public schools to charter schools and schools established directly as charter schools. State schools that have turned into charter schools have the opportunity to use more financial resources. This is mostly observed in the amount of money spent per student and the fees paid to instructors. In public schools converted into charter schools, the annual fee paid to the instructor is higher than the newly established charter schools (American Federation of Teachers, 2004). However, the newly established charter schools are able to employ more part-time instructors. As the stages of establishing the curriculum, determining the education system and creating financial resources are often determined during the formation of charter schools, charter schools have been closed shortly after their opening (Griffin & Wohlstetter)., 2001, p.336). In the field of financial control of charter schools, many states have developed some practices to prevent the donation provided to these schools from reaching excessive amounts. For example, he can transfer up to ten percent of his current budget to the next year's budget and buy special equipment with a maximum of five percent of the budget, or return the surplus to the district administration or state (Center for Education Reform, 2004).

The period in which the school year begins coincides with the period in which the most resources are spent. In this case, some charter schools borrow short-term loans from private institutions or government-created funds (American Federation of Teachers, 2004), but a school may not have a strong enough budget to borrow. For this reason, some practices have been developed by the state or states to transfer funds to charter schools when necessary.

Funding is provided to many charter schools within the framework of a certain fundraising regulation set by each state. According to this regulation, the financing needed by the schools is generally provided by three different methods. These:

- 1) Determining the expenditure to be made per student.
- 2) Determining the number of students requiring high-cost education.
- 3) Providing financing for the education program with the services provided to the student such as transportation and food.

Some states allow the charter school to set their own methods and retain their own financial controller. In addition, schools that receive large amounts of federal funding have to comply with some federal accounting and auditing standards. School entrepreneurs should consult their state's education units and other financial management professionals when making their financial systems.

The revenues of charter schools are divided into three groups as federal funds, state funds and other funds.

These groups are:

Federal funds; Distributed directly by the US Department of Education or through state or local education units. These funds are Initial Aid, Personal Disabilities Education Movement, Comprehensive School Reform Implementation Program, Twenty-first Century Public Learning Centers Program and Ministry of Justice and Health education support funds. Programs that provide support funds are published on the National Charter School Resource Center page (National Charter School Resource Center, 2018).

State funds; it mainly depends on the number of student enrollments (for example, average daily class attendance).

Other sources of funding; it can come from private and non-profit communities. Sometimes charter schools cooperate with local higher education organizations for day-to-day use in some areas they can benefit from. Foundations donate money, technology or product supply to charter schools. Some companies and organizations donate to schools that use their products. Companies also help students who are talented in their fields. There are also funds that companies transfer to teachers.

PRIVATE SCHOOL REFORM WORKS IN INTERNATIONAL AREA QATAR & GEORGIA CASE

In addition to public schools, some countries have also made some initiatives and carried out activities on the establishment and development of private schools. In this section, Qatar and Georgia involved in private school reform work are presented as an example.

Development of School Funding System for K - 12 Reform in Qatar

Education is a critical component of any nation's effort to prepare its youth for civic engagement and the global economy. The leaders of the Arab country of the Gulf, Qatar, saw education as the key to Qatar's economic and social progress. However, the education system of the country was rigid and resistant to reform, which has not been able to produce quality results for a long time. Qatari leaders approached the RAND Corporation in 2001 (Research and Development) and requested that the education system (K-12) be examined through the education system. He demanded that options be proposed to build a first-class system consistent with Qatar's social and political change and initiatives. The Emir of Qatar issued Decree No.37 in 2002, establishing a Higher Education Council (SEC), which will become the highest authority in Qatar's education sector. Most of the reform focused on K - 12 education. Efforts were made to decentralize authority and increase flexibility, based on the principles of autonomy, accountability, diversity and choice in education.

Trends in Financial Resource Allocation in Reform

One of the most important parts of reform was how and in what way financial resources were spent. In this context, the expenditures made were monitored.

Total Expenditure on Reform

Three periods were considered to document total expenditure on reform;

1. Planning phase (April 2003 - March 2004)
2. Beginning and first year of independent school activity (April 2004 - March 2005)
3. Second year of independent school business (April 2005 - March 2006).

Funding flows directly from the Institute of Education to independent schools and includes three broad categories of support. Pre-operation expenses; start-up funds, enrollment-based per-student allocations and grants awarded to fund other special projects or meet unusual needs. In addition, schools can earn a limited amount of various incomes on their own (Guarino et al. 2009, p. 15).

Start-up Funds

These funds were only given to schools that were in the first year of activity from the day the contract was signed, at the beginning of the academic year until the school was opened, and covered the costs of that period.

Initial funds are generally;

- Administrative staff and teachers' allowances, Professional development and training,
- Recruitment of teachers and students,
- Covers expenses such as consultation fees and library development.

Initial funds do not include capital expenditures or supplies such as laboratories, furniture and computers provided directly by the Institute of Education. As of the 2006 - 2007 school year, the Institute of Education initial funds are offered as an advance under the per-student allocation to schools.

Allocations per Student

Schools receive quarterly per-student funding to cover operating expenses based on enrollment levels. The amount awarded to schools depends on the level of the school (primary education, preparatory or secondary education) and students with special needs are overpaid by 20%. The complexes receive a mix of allocations per student based on the number of students enrolled in each level.

Other Funds

Other funds; benefits, project revenues, cafeteria, etc. consists of incomes. These funds are listed below.

Aids; between 2004 and 2005, schools were given the opportunity to apply for grants to cover the "non-operational costs required to encourage creativity and innovation" when designing a school. Grants generally cover large projects such as specialized technological equipment, computer software, language programs, textbooks, special needs and other activities not included in the operating budget. However, grants were discontinued in 2005-2006 and were not offered in subsequent school years.

Various income; these revenues represent other income that schools can earn, such as cafeteria income and book sales.

- Other funds in first generation schools; it consisted of grants (6%), starting funds (5%) and miscellaneous income (2%).
- Second generation schools received 94% of their total funding in the form of allocations per student.
- Third, the system provided an incentive for operators to generate surplus, as independent schools were initially established as profit-making institutions.
- Fourth, the system lacked direct incentives to improve quality, as accountability mechanisms were not linked to academic performance.

- Fifth, the requirement that all costs be approved by the Finance Office may have led to a reduction in expenditure. Finally, schools may have been over-funded and did not need the money given to them (Guarino et al.2009, p.18).

Evaluation of School Finance System in Reform

Some prominent items in the reform study are as follows:

Transparency: A school financing system should be based on an open accounting system that tracks the use of funds.

Equality: A school funding system should provide sufficient resources to meet the needs of all students equally.

Qualification: A school funding system should provide sufficient funding to support excellent education.

Efficiency: A school financing system should offer effective education models at the most economical price.

Accountability: A school funding system should ensure that public fund recipients produce a quality of education commensurate with the funding received.

Stability: A school financing system should balance the stability of funding required to enable schools to invest in high quality education delivery with the flexibility to adapt to ongoing evidence-based needs assessments.

Competence

There is no universally accepted definition of qualification in educational funding. There are four main approaches to determine the level of funding sufficient to achieve the desired results (Augenblick et al., 1997; Guthrie & Springer, 2007, p.39): These are called historical approach, professional judgment approach, econometric approach and successful school approach.

Historical approach; it only sets new funding levels based on past levels. It starts by setting a baseline cost level using the actual expenses of a particular school set. Its advantages include simplicity and predictability. A disadvantage arises if the expenditures made in previous years were not really sufficient or too high. This method does not have the ability to distinguish between adequate funding and past results to achieve the desired results.

Professional judgment approach (Professional decision approach); Achieving a high quality learning environment relies on a panel of experts to decide the levels of resources required. Once the type and quantity of resources have been determined, costs are allocated. The costs are then added up to determine the total expense amount. Although logical, the professional judgment approach has some disadvantages: Firstly; there are no clear selection criteria for the expert panel. Latter; whether the panel is composed of educators or financial professionals, conflicts of interest are likely. Thirdly; the decisions taken are likely to be highly subjective and not associated with productivity (Augenblick et al., 1997; Guthrie & Springer, 2007, p.40).

Econometric (cost function) approach; examines the relationship between costs and training outcomes using econometric modeling. Data on achievement in costs and school characteristics (including students' socioeconomic characteristics) are collected. Costs are then correlated with success and school characteristics in a statistical model. Using the resulting statistical equation, estimated costs are calculated for a desired level of success. The econometric approach is problematic for several reasons: Firstly; data is based on current resource usage that may or may not be efficient. Latter; the results are very sensitive to the way the model is determined (Guthrie & Springer, 2007, p. 40). Thirdly; If the desired levels of achievement are much higher in the data than those obtained in the school sample, the equation should estimate costs based on insufficient evidence that could lead to non-sample estimation bias. Finally; If resources and achievement are only weakly related, the model can be quite

misleading. If this relationship is not strong, the model will produce very high and possibly inflated estimates about the amount of funds required to achieve the desired small increases in student achievement (Hanushek, 2006, p. 41).

Successful schools approach; It examines the actual expenditures in schools that are seen as successful in achieving desired results by adapting to factors that lead to prejudice such as having students from high-income families. In this approach, high performing schools are defined first. Average expenditure in these schools is calculated and used as proof of adequate spending levels. An advantage of this method is that it can examine the use of various types of resources in high-performing schools and compare with the use of the same resources in low-performing schools. For example, the student spending, student-teacher ratios, administrative expenditures and education expenditures can be examined. One prominent disadvantage is that it requires the most successful schools to actually achieve desired performance levels (Guarino et al. 2009, p. 41). The successful schools approach has been taken as the most appropriate methodology to be applied to the Qatar context. Because it is based on real spending rather than hypothetical spending patterns.

Simply, the way to make a measure of the value added by the school is to take the difference between a recent and previous test score for each child and average those differences by school. A more detailed method of constructing such a measure is to adjust previous scores and other student characteristics in the multivariate statistical regression model if possible. By checking students' previous year scores, we can better determine the net value added by the school in the current year and reduce the impact of performance relative to the child's ability level at the beginning of the year. As a disadvantage, situations such as adjusting child characteristics will further isolate the contribution to learning offered by the school.

Productivity

Productivity assessment is based on determining the appropriate variation between school performance and production costs. This determination is difficult because few schools perform at high levels. Hence, methods of relating activity to spending levels are necessary to characterize relative operational efficiency in schools. We can think of economic efficiency as the ratio of benefits to costs. Theoretically, a school is considered most efficient by finding the point that the additional benefit of spending an extra fund is less than the additional cost. If adding more funds produces a marginally lower return, spending more is not efficient. However, efficiency is a difficult concept to handle. Efficiency is approached more intuitively by first determining the desired target performance level and then determining the minimum amount of funds that will generate that level. First step; to determine school performance levels using methods that adjust student characteristics similar to those outlined in the previous section. Next step; to determine the level of school performance that is accepted as a proficiency Third step; to select a range of schools that meet qualification standards and examine resource use. If enough schools can be defined as high performance, it will be possible to compare expenditures between these schools and exclude high spending schools from the calculation of average expenditure; because they are less efficient than high performing, low spending schools. The resulting average expenditure estimate can be considered efficient.

Accountability

A key element of New Era Education reform in Qatar is holding independent schools accountable to society for financial responsibility and student learning. Accountability for the proper use of funds is based on two mechanisms: financial monitoring and school selection. The first includes financial oversight by the Finance Office. The second involves parents choosing the schools their children attend. The Finance Office holds schools financially accountable through a monitoring process that tracks school expenditures and the operator's resource allocation decisions. It does this in three ways:

First: external controls have been used since the beginning of the reform.

Latter; schools should develop an internal monitoring system as part of their overall management strategy. This system involves designing a set of policies and procedures related to financial issues,

budget development calendar, a computer-based accounting system, payroll services system and banking regulations.

Thirdly; The Finance Office has developed a set of mandatory budget guidelines for staff covering financial transactions and salary coefficients. Schools submit a series of reports throughout the year directly to the Finance Office. It can then assess compliance with these guidelines and work with schools to make sure they comply with the above reporting requirements.

The rules in force in 2004 - 2005 and 2005 - 2006 are as follows:

- Operators should allocate about 60% of the training budget for teaching staff salaries and expenses.
- Schools are encouraged to allocate more than 17% of their budget to administration expenses.
- Schools can switch from any line item to another up to 10% of the budget amount. Any movement between line items beyond the above limits must be approved by the Finance Office.
- Operators cannot charge tuition fees for students who are entitled to receive state funding per student (Guarino et al. 2009, p. 48).

Summary

Summary information on the Qatar education reform is given below.

- Independent school operating costs accounted for 37% and 48% of total reform expenditure in 2004-2005 and 2005-2006, respectively.
- In the second year of operation, revenues decreased while expenditure increased for Generation Independent schools.
- It has been observed that independent schools hesitated to spend in their first years of activity, but adjusted their expenditures to some extent in their second year.
- Nearly all Independent schools gave a surplus as a percentage of their operating income.
 - Staff expenditures make up the majority (about 82%) of the operational expenditure of independent schools, while teaching staff accounts for about three-quarters of all staff expenditure.

Georgia School Funding System and Equity

In an interview with David Saginadze, Head of the Economy Department of the Georgian Ministry of Education and Science (SFSandERR, 2014, p. 84), he stated that private schools were established in Georgia in the early 1990s. Their number almost doubled in the period 2003-2006. When the per capita financing system was activated as of 2006, it states that there are 270 private education schools.

Private Schools and Funding Formula

Four important education policies have been created specifically for financing private schools in Georgia:

- Establishing market values in education can have a positive effect on the overall performance of general education schools.
- In addition to providing free general (basic, primary and secondary) public education to every child in Georgia, the government can ensure that inequalities in access to private education and the quality of education received by the student do not depend on the financial capacity of the family.

- One of the main drivers of the training voucher policy is commitment to freedom of choice in Georgia. It ensures consumer choice and personal development by stating that “the state will protect the freedom of choice in education for a student and parent” (Law of Georgia on General Education, 2005, Chapter III, Article-23).
- Providing public funds for private education has been seen as an effective way to strengthen public-private partnerships in education. Perhaps believing in the superiority of private education providers over public schools, the Georgian government has sought to create incentives and favorable conditions for the expansion of special education in general education (SFSandERR 2014, p.25).

This section analyzes the private schools financing system in the context of different education policy. Changes in the education funding system in 2011 resulted in changes in the financing of private schools:

- In the previous funding model, private schools were entitled to the same amount of student funding as public schools. All private schools receive fixed funding per student (this fund is less than the student voucher amount in public schools).
- Private school students cannot benefit from additional public services like their peers in public schools. For example, the government provides netbooks to all first graders except those enrolled in private schools.
- Since 2013, the government has introduced the free textbooks system. Public school students receive their books from the school, provided that they return them at the end of the school year. Students in private schools have to buy their own books.

The above mentioned changes may have the following negative consequences:

- To prevent the development of the private sector in the general education system.
- Keeping socially vulnerable students of private schools in unequal conditions compared to public school students.

The current financing system of private schools and the distribution of tuition fees cause problems in several ways:

- Parents of students in private schools that do not have fees or are dependent on donations need additional government support, as in public schools. The new financing system creates no opportunity for private school development.
- The private school sector is mostly developed in Tbilisi. Thus, the private school system has not developed in other regions and rural areas.
- Additional funding is provided to higher education schools in the form of public vouchers for each enrolled student, which has no effect on the tuition fee paid by parents. Therefore, parents and students cannot benefit from the public money allocated to each student. This public funding is an additional income for private schools. This additional funding does not contribute to the development of private schools either, as is given to higher education, these schools are already very developed and do not need additional support from the state. Such schools are mostly (90%) concentrated in Tbilisi.

Public and Private Sector Competition

- The current funding system does not create favorable conditions for creating competition between private and public schools and ultimately promoting high quality in both private and public schools.
- Private schools in the region are less competitive than public schools for the following reasons:
- Private schools in the region cannot provide free textbooks and netbooks to their students as in public schools.
- Public school teachers in the regions have better working conditions than their peers in private schools.
- Private schools in the regions are not competitive; mainly serve as day care centers and are perceived **by parents** and their students as a place of residence (this is especially true for schools established by religious organizations).

Policy Development Recommendations

SFSandERR 2014, p. According to 137 report, the research revealed significant gaps, challenges and improvements in Georgia's general education funding system. The main problem is the gap between education policy and funding. The state finances non-Georgian schools, schools in rural areas, village schools, small schools, without any change or improvement in the quality of education and training in these schools. The lack of link between financing and education reform is the main problem of Georgia's education system.

The research revealed the three most important problems of the funding formula, and recommendations are based on research findings in these three directions:

- Funding of private schools.
- Financing non-Georgian schools and sectors.
 - Financing small schools with 1 to 169 students.

Financing Private Schools

According to the findings of the research data, the situations related to school financing are explained below in 3 items.

- Preparing a need-based model for supporting the development of private schools and financing private schools... The research revealed that there are big differences between the tuition fees of private schools.
- The research found that the current financing system does not create favorable conditions for creating competition between private and public schools, and ultimately improving quality in both private and public schools. Public schools are less competitive than private schools.
- Promoting the establishment of free or voucher schools in Georgia... Schools will be awarded government vouchers and low lease agreements for the school grounds and will be run as semi-private schools. This policy is important for Georgia to privatize education services and strengthen schooling in Georgia. For example, if different decisions are made regarding private schools, voucher schools can also be opened in the same building. This situation can increase the quality of teaching in schools and thus encourage the development of the private sector in all regions of Georgia.

Financing Non-Georgian Schools

Bilingual education criteria should be introduced in the financing system of non-Georgian schools and non-Georgian sectors. According to the needs of designing and implementing bilingual education programs, schools should be provided with additional resources and the language needs of students should be met. The Georgian government provides additional funding for the language needs of minority students. Non-Georgian schools receive a standard coupon with a coefficient of 1.13 and a school voucher with a coefficient of 1.14 to non-Georgian schools. The implementation of bilingual education programs by non-Georgian schools remains a major obstacle. Ineffective use of additional funding in non-Georgian schools is confirmed by school exit exam results and general skills exam results in university entrance exams (SFSandERR 2014, p. 141).

Financing Small Schools with 1 - 169 Students

- Optimization of expenses and optimal management of the schools mentioned above in schools with 1 - 169 students... Research revealed that the government allocates a lot of money to such schools without any influence. The main problem is the gap between education reform and funding. Structural, institutional and instructional reforms are needed to bridge the gap between students' academic achievements and to create equal educational opportunities.
- The financing system should finance schools in a transparent, measurable way in schools with 1 to 169 students and eliminate inequalities in funding. The research revealed that the schools receiving the calculated funding were not equally funded. Some schools are over funded while others are underfunded. These schools have almost the same number of students, the same geographical location, the language of instruction, the number of buildings, and the student distribution among different classes.

Fund Management Development by Public Schools

- In order to encourage school autonomy in fundraising and budget expenditures, bureaucratic. This issue is an important problem especially for rural and mountainous region schools. Procurement procedures should be simplified and made into a transparent, open and easily managed procurement system. The study shows that schools face problems with expenditure when they receive additional funding or save on student finance per capita. Also, due to purchasing procedures, schools are often unable to purchase the desired product. As a result, they begin to accumulate unused financial resources rather than spend resources for the needs of the school.
- It is recommended to provide 3% of the annual budget as an additional resource to schools that fully spend the allocated resources. Each school should provide a detailed spending proposal with a timetable for the use of additional financial resources. This will enable schools to meet their needs. At the same time, the ministry will receive information about possible changes to be implemented in the education financing system. In such an approach, an irrelevant financial accumulation problem will arise in some schools. Schools with very high financial savings should also be asked to propose affordable spending.
- A system of Teacher Salary Ranges According to the Monthly Expense Ratio of a certain region / Each region should be developed.
- It should be ensured that school administration criteria are developed, the bureaucratic approval procedures of the school personal and salary fund should be eliminated, the administrative expenses and teachers' salaries should be increased, schools should be given more autonomy to use their own income.

- It should be ensured that the number of staff is defined not only by the number of schools but also by the area of the school building and the number of units / classrooms.
- Special programs for IDPs (International Development Program) and socially vulnerable students should be created according to their needs.
- Schools need to improve their capacity for the participation of disabled students.
- The research found that schools with 1270 or more students have more financial savings than small schools. It is important to recalculate the amount of basic funding to make each school category equally competitive in development (SFSandERR 2014, p. 143).

CURRENT EDUCATION INVESTMENT SUPPORTS IN TURKEY

Current investment incentives in all areas of Turkey are carried out by the Ministry of Industry and Technology, Directorate General for Promotion and Foreign Capital. Infrastructure and personnel employment incentives for education are also provided by the same General Directorate (Ministry of Industry and Technology, 2020).

Investment Incentive Systems

Complementarity relationship between public investments and private sector investments will be increased; public infrastructure investments will be made to pave the way for private sector investments that create high added value, increase employment and contribute to the reduction of the current account deficit, and to increase productivity capacity (CBSBB - 2019, p.102). Our country's long-term development policies, economic growth, information society, international competitiveness, institutionalization, sustainability, inclusiveness, etc. It is created with a multifaceted approach in dimensions and is implemented in the public and private sectors with a holistic perspective. The incentive system, which entered into force with the decision of the Council of Ministers dated 15.06.2012 and numbered 2012/3305, consists of 4 different applications. These applications; General Incentive Practices, Regional Incentive Applications, Incentive of Priority Investments, Incentive of Strategic Investments.

Table -3 - Table of Support Items to be Provided.

Support Elements	General Incentive	Regional Incentive Applications	Primary Investment Incentive	Incentive of Strategic Investments
VAT Exception	✓	✓	✓	✓
Customs Tax Exemption	✓	✓	✓	✓
Tax Discount		✓	✓	✓
Insurance Premium Employer's Share		✓	✓	✓
Income Tax withholding Support	✓	✓	✓	✓
Insurance Premium (Labor shares) Support ⁵		✓	✓	✓
Interest or Margin Support ⁶		✓	✓	✓
Investment Location Grant		✓	✓	✓

Ministry of Industry and Technology, 2020, p.5

⁵ If the investment is made in the 6th Region, in the OIZs in the provinces of the 4th and 5th regions within the scope of the Attraction Centers Program and in the OIZs of Kilis, it is provided to strategic investments supported under the Technology Oriented Industry Move Program (TOSHP).

⁶ It is provided if the investment is realized in Regional Incentive Practices in regions 3, 4, 5 or 6

Support elements are shown according to the incentive practices in Table-3. Priority investment incentive supports are also used in education investments.

Support Elements

Value added tax exemption; It is applied in the form of non-payment of value added tax for the sale and lease of investment goods, machinery and equipment, software and intangible rights within the scope of the Incentive Certificate to be procured domestically and from abroad. Customs duty exemption; It is applied in the form of non-payment of customs duty for machinery and equipment, investment goods, to be procured from abroad within the scope of the Incentive Certificate. Tax relief is the discounted implementation of income or corporate tax until it reaches the amount of the anticipated contribution for the investment Insurance premium employer's share support; The insurance premium employer's share, which must be paid for the additional employment provided by the investment within the scope of the Incentive Certificate, corresponding to the minimum wage is covered by the Ministry. Income tax withholding support; Cancellation of the income tax withholding determined for the additional employment provided by the investment within the scope of the Incentive Certificate. It is only foreseen in the incentive certificates issued for investments to be made in the 6th region and strategic investments supported under TOSHP. Insurance premium (employee share) support; The portion of the insurance premium workers' share corresponding to the minimum wage that must be paid for the additional employment provided by the investment within the scope of the Incentive Certificate is covered by the Ministry. It is only foreseen in the incentive certificates issued for regional and strategic investments to be made in the 6th region and strategic investments supported under TOSHP. Interest or dividend support; It is a financing support provided for investment loans with a term of at least one year used within the scope of the Incentive Certificate, and a certain part of the interest or profit share to be paid for the loan used up to 70% of the fixed investment amount registered in the incentive certificate is covered by the Ministry. Investment location allocation; It is the allocation of an investment location within the framework of the procedures and principles determined by the Ministry of Finance for the investments with incentive certificates. Value added tax refund; is the refund of the VAT collected for the building - construction expenditures realized within the scope of the Strategic Investments with a fixed investment amount of more than 500 million Turkish Liras.

Table- 4-Regional Table Showing the Development Level of the Provinces in Terms of Incentive Applications

1 st Region	2 nd 1 st Region	3 rd 1 st Region	4 th 1 st Region	5 th 1 st Region	6 th 1 st Region
Ankara	Adana	Balıkesir	Afyonkarahisar	Adıyaman	Ağrı
Antalya	Aydın	Bilecik	Amasya	Aksaray	Ardahan
Bursa	Bolu	Burdur	Artvin	Bayburt	Batman
Eskişehir	Çanakkale	Gaziantep	Bartın	Çankırı	Bingöl
İstanbul	Denizli	Karabük	Çorum	Erzurum	Bitlis
İzmir	Edirne	Karaman	Düzce	Giresun	Diyarbakır
Kocaeli	Isparta	Manisa	Elazığ	Gümüşhane	Hakkâri
Muğla	Kayseri	Mersin	Erzincan	Kahramanmaraş	Iğdır
	Kırklareli	Samsun	Hatay	Kilis	Kars
	Konya	Trabzon	Kastamonu	Niğde	Mardin
	Sakarya	Uşak	Kırıkkale	Ordu	Muş
	Tekirdağ	Zonguldak	Kırşehir	Osmaniye	Siirt
	Yalova		Kütahya	Sinop	Şanlıurfa
			Malatya	Tokat	Şırnak
			Nevşehir	Tunceli	Van
			Rize	Yozgat	
			Sivas		
8	13	12	17	16	15

Ministry of Industry and Technology, 2020, p. 6.

The development region of 81 provinces is shown in Table-4.

Table-5-Support Items Provided in Regional Incentive Practices

Support Elements		Regions						
		I	II	III	IV	V	VI	
VAT Exception		+	+	+	+	+	+	
Customs Tax Exception		+	+	+	+	+	+	
Tax Relief	Contribution Rate ⁷ (%)	OIZ and IZ ⁸ Out	15	20	25	30	40	50
		OIZ and IZ in	20	25	30	40	50	55
Tax Premium Employer's share support	The duration of support (as years)	OIZ and IZ out	2	3	5	6	7	10
		OIZ and IZ in	3	5	6	7	10	12
Investment Location Allocation (as years)		+	+	+	+	+	+	
Interest or Margin Support	Domestic loan	-	-	3score	4score	5score	7score	
	Foreign currency indexed Credit	-	-	1 score	1score	2score	2score	
Insurance premiums (Worker's share) Support		-	-	-	-	-	10 year	
Income Tax withholding Support		-	-	-	-	-	10 year	

Ministry of Industry and Technology, 2020. p. 7

Table-5 shows the support elements provided in regional incentive applications. There are supports given in line with the investments to be made in the regions.

Education Infrastructure Supports

Investments made in priority investment issues are supported by the 5th Region supports regardless of the region. Education is also among the priority investments. Therefore, even if investments are made in education in regions 1, 2, 3, 4, incentives for the 5th region are benefited (Ministry of Industry and Technology, Investment Incentive Brochure, 2020). Supporting education investments in a way that provides opportunities to the private sector by expanding it stands out as an important element. As in all investment incentives, an Investment Incentive Certificate should be obtained in education investments. Investment Incentive Certificate; It is a document that shows the subject of the investment, the location of the investment, the incentive to be used by the investor and the amount of the investment. The investor who has received the Investment Incentive Certificate benefits from the support mechanisms. The incentive certificate is a document that contains the characteristic values of the investment and provides the opportunity to benefit from the support elements recorded on it if the investment is carried out in accordance with these values and the determined conditions, and is issued for the investments to be realized in accordance with the objectives of the decision. The duration of the Investment Incentive Certificate is 3 years (İpekyolu Development Agency, 2018).

MONE - Education and Training Support (2018 - 2019 Example)

Education and training support for students who will study in private schools within the scope of the Law on Private Education Institutions numbered 5580 was firstly given based on the article published in the Official Gazette dated 07 August 2014 and numbered 29081 (OOKGM, 2018, p.

Education support continued for 5 years from 2014 - 2015 academic year to 2018 - 2019 academic year. "It has been announced that education and training support will not be given to students who will study for the first time in private schools as of the 2019-2020 academic year. The support of students who received incentive payments in previous years will continue until they graduate (MONE, 2019) ". In this sense, there is no incentive system for students who are newly enrolled in private

⁷ Within the scope of investment incentive certificates issued for the manufacturing industry (US-97 Code: 15 -37), the investment contribution rate for investment expenditures to be realized between 1/1/2017 and 31/12/2022 is 15% to the investment contribution rate valid in each region. By adding points, the tax reduction rate is applied as 100% in all regions and the rate of the investment contribution amount that can be used during the investment period is 100%.

⁸ IZ: Investments made in the Industrial Zone for the manufacturing industry.

schools by the Ministry of National Education. Finally, in 2018 - 2019 academic year, education and training support was provided with the decision published in the Official Gazette dated 12 August 2018 and numbered 30507. The number of students who received educational support in the 2018 - 2019 academic year is shown in Table-7.

Table-6-Types of Schools Provided Education and Training Support, Support Amounts and Number of Students

S. No	School Type	The Amount of Support(TL)	Number of students to be supported for the first time
1	Preschool	3.290,00	6.000
2	Primary	3.960,00	15.000
3	Secondary	4.610,00	15.000
4	High School	4.610,00	15.000
5	Basic High School	3.960,00	24.000
Total			75.000

Official Gazette, 12 Ağs.2018, Number: 30507

As stated in Table-6, according to the data published in the Official Gazette, the number of students benefiting from education support for the first time is 75000.

Table-7-Socio-Economic Development Levels Coefficients

Socio-Economic Level	Development	1. Region	2. Region	3. Region	4. Region	5. Region	6. Region
Coefficiency		0,95	0,95	1,00	1,00	1,20	1,30

Official Gazette, 12 Ağs.2018, Number: 30507

The coefficients in Table-7 are used in the distribution of the students to be given education and training support according to their socio-economic development levels.

Education and Training Support Application E-Guide

In this guide, the prominent items regarding the conditions under which education support will be provided in the 2018 - 2019 academic year are discussed (OOKGM, 2018, p.5).

Highlights in General Conditions

- The education and training support fee of the students who are entitled to receive education and training support will be paid to the schools where they study, 35% in November, 35% in February and 30% in June.
- Education and training support will not be given to students who receive scholarships at the rate of 51% or more of the annual fee announced by the institution or for free.
- Those who are eligible to receive education and training support among students studying in a pre-school academic year, primary school, secondary school and secondary school types will benefit from this support until the end of the school's education period. However, except those who certify that these students have been treated for a long time with a medical report, those who repeat a grade in their class will lose their right to benefit from education and training support.

Application Conditions

- Students who can apply for educational support must meet the conditions stated below.
- To be a citizen of Republic of Turkey (T.C.),
- Being born between 17 March 2013 and 17 September 2014 in pre-school education,
- Having the enrollment requirements as of 30 September 2018 in the first year of primary school,
- Having the enrollment requirements for secondary school or imam-hatip secondary school as of September 17, 2018, for those who will continue to fifth grade,
- Having the registration requirements of secondary education institutions for those who will continue secondary education,
- Not repeating a grade at the end of the 2017-2018 academic year while receiving education and training support
- Being registered in the middle classes of public / private primary, secondary and secondary schools,
- Having the registration and transfer conditions of the type of school for which they want to receive education and training support.

Placement Processes

- In education and training support placement procedures, placement scores will be evaluated separately at each grade level.
- In the determination of the students to be given education and training support, if there is equality in the total score determined in the Determination Form of the Students who can be given Education and Training Support, the student who has a high success score at the end of the previous year, and if the equality is not broken, the student with less unexcused absenteeism will be preferred. If the equality is still not broken, the younger student will be preferred.
- Students of up to 25% of the school's support quota are placed in each class level. More than 25% of the building quota will not be able to place students at each grade level.
- 20% of the education and training support quota of the school to each of the 9th, 10th and 11th grade levels in basic high schools; Students will be placed in the 12th grade up to 40% of the school's support quota.
- Students who choose the private school from outside and students who are enrolled in the private school will be placed in the vacant parts of the building quotas.
- As a result of students' preferences, two placement scores will be announced for the respective private school. The lowest scores on placement; Students who are placed outside of the institution and registered students of the school will have the lowest scores.
- There will be no placement process within the scope of support above the quotas of schools supported by education and training.
- No additional preference will be taken for the Additional Placement process, and according to the first preferences, the vacant quotas of the schools will be placed in line with the above principles. Among the applicants, incentives were given by ranking from the student with the highest score to the lowest according to the Student Determination Form.

Student Evaluation Criteria;

- Students' Success
- Family's Total Monthly Income
- Other Children Studying in the Family
- The Situation of the Mother and Father

- Disciplinary Actions
- The children of primary and secondary education age of those who are considered as war or duty disabled, as specified in Article 13 of the Law, and children who are given protection, care or shelter decisions

NEW MODEL RECOMMENDATIONS AND RESULTS

This section contains model suggestions and results regarding the research.

New Model Suggestions

In Turkey many infrastructure support, including investment in education is provided through the Ministry of Industry and Technology. Considering the research results, countries provide different types of funding to private schools. In our country, educational incentives can be given in the context of development regions, except infrastructure.

MONE can establish a 'provincial private school board' in provinces before private school incentives. It can be ensured that there are 2 academicians, a financial expert, a lawyer and an auditor from the field of education in the provincial board of directors. Provincial special school administrative boards are determined by the governorship and the chairman of the board can be appointed by the governor among the members. The number of members can be increased by the governor according to the number of private schools. All private schools that have signed contracts may be obliged to make transactions from the same bank to be determined in the province. It should be mandatory to examine the financial situation of the contracting institution. Institutions benefiting from incentives should have to make 90% of their expenditures for the educational institution they receive incentives. Exams can be arranged to determine the academic achievement of private schools through the provincial private school board. In this way, the relationship between the support provided and academic success will be followed.

Training Vouchers

The provinces were divided into education regions within the scope of the MONE - Education Regions Directive updated in 2008. In this context, student disadvantage situations in educational regions, socio-economic criteria, monthly income, etc. Training voucher support can be given via a form prepared with criteria (similar to the form in Table-10). It is announced that the students in which region will benefit from the training vouchers within the framework of the projection determined by the relevant province. It can be determined for the class levels where students are concentrated in line with the needs. The purpose of this support is to reduce the student density. Parents can use these vouchers at private schools in designated education districts.

The second approach in training vouchers is to encourage investments to be made in education regions with low success. For example; It is the support to be given to institutions that want to open a school in a region with low success and declare that they will increase their student success with a central examination. These institutions receive free support up to a certain student as initial support. Education expenses of all students are covered by the state. With the results of the central exam and the school status report, which measures the student success at the end of the year, it is decided whether to continue school education supports.

Start Supports

The private, which has contracted with the state, is supported by the state at the first opening of the school. MONE decides in which educational districts support will be provided in line with its student density and needs. Among the sector representatives that will invest here, suitable ones are determined. Among these criteria, being a domestic investor and being a sustainable institution should be among the priorities. Student support per person is provided to the institution in initial support. It is ensured that schools benefit from the facilities of other public institutions free of charge, like public schools. In addition, teachers in public institutions can attend classes in private schools for 10 hours

according to the 41st article of the MONE Regulation on Private Education Institutions. In this context, in private schools with initial support, teachers can be given the opportunity to attend classes for up to 20 hours. This support application can only be valid for the first 2 years of the school opening. In this way, the newly opened institution will pay insurance premiums for the first 2 years for the teacher. is exempted from financial liabilities.

School Grant Support Applications

The state provides grant support for the development of its own strategies in many fields. In this context, grant support can be given in the field of education. The following situations may be taken into account in the grant support to be made through the joint call procedure of the Ministry of Industry and Technology and the Ministry of National Education:

- ✓ Region investment situations.
- ✓ Socio-economic indicators of the region.
- ✓ The number of schools in the educational area.
- ✓ School student density.
- ✓ Classroom density.
- ✓ 10-year history of the number of schools and students in the region.
- ✓ Regional priority status of education investment.

The grant program to be supported is determined in May every year through the Strategic Plan of the Ministry of National Education and the Ministry of Industry and Technology.

Grant investments; infrastructure, VAT reduction, student incentives, etc. It is given as a package and in the form of a grant.

For example, a province in the 1st development zone can already benefit from the 5th Region investments. In addition to these investments, student incentives, stationery, equipment, etc. Support can be provided as a package by adding alternatives. The limitations of the support are arranged every year in the grant application conditions to be prepared. Thus, regardless of the investment region in which it is located, it will be possible to make regional education support investments according to the changing situations in education every year.

Common Issues

Regardless of where incentives or support is given to private schools, the following situations should be considered:

Productivity: At first the desired performance level should be determined and a budget (fund) should be allocated accordingly. In the evaluations, the differences between the performance level determined first and the next performance level should be measured. School benefit / cost ratios should be determined.

Supervision: The school must inspect at certain times. The differences should be observed by taking the averages of the initial investment costs and the following years' costs financially. It is necessary to have a financial plan regarding the financial sustainability of the school. The institution should be able to transfer at most 10% of the budget to the next year's budget. The remaining budget should be transferred to the public budget.

Results

Since the charter schools model applied in the USA is subjected to year-end evaluations, success rates are high. Supporting schools according to the difference between the cost in schools and student success is an indicator of this.

Since private schools in the People's Republic of China are followed with a strict financial discipline, it is very difficult for institutions or organizations without financial power to open and run private

schools. In this context, the state does not provide financial support to private schools. However, in terms of fiscal discipline, it has been observed that China's studies are effective in controlling school financial structures. Since private schools are not financially supported in the UK, private sector investments in education and the number of private schools are relatively low compared to public schools. Since privileges to open private schools (financial support, tax discount, etc.) are given to charities, the number of private schools opened by these institutions is high.

The number of private schools increased with the implementation of the Private School Promotion Incentive Law in Japan in 2007 and the support of private schools. The establishment and management of private schools through school companies, the requirement of auditors in schools, and the tight financial control of private schools have made private schools more disciplined. In France, the appointment of teachers with a central examination to be able to work in public or private schools has enabled a standard teacher level to be determined. In addition, all the rights of teachers working in a public or private school are the same. This situation puts the emphasis on equality in France. In France, it is seen that the number of private schools is high due to the financial contributions provided to private schools by providing support such as VAT reduction. In the initiative of education reform in private schools in Qatar, the start-up funds were supported by per student allocations and other funds (business etc. incomes). In the reform, the criteria of competence, efficiency and accountability came to the fore in the assessment of financial situations. For private school reform, the relationship between academic achievement and education cost has not been fully determined. For this reason, private school reform has been stalled for revision.

Similar to per capita financial support (public voucher) or contour loading, which started to be implemented in private schools in Georgia in 2006, additional supports were provided to private schools. Although these supports partially led to an increase in the number of private schools, a clear situation could not be revealed about the success of the students.

REFERENCES

- American Federation of Teachers, "Paying for the Vision. Charter School Revenue and Expenditures", <http://www.aft.org/charterfinance/PayingfortheVision.pdf> (Date of access: 03.03.2020).
- Augenblick, John G.; John L.; Myers, and Amy B. Anderson (1997). "Equity and Adequacy in School Funding, The Future of Children—Financing Schools", Journal Article, 7(3). (Winter, 1997), PrincetonUniversity, doi: 10.2307/1602446.
- Archer, J. (2003) "Magnet Schools among Winners in Tight Budget", Education Week, 23(1).
- Bertola G.(2015),"France's Almost Public Private Schools", with input from Pierre Courtioux,s.1 https://cepr.org/sites/default/files/events/4579_BERTOLA%20-%20France%27s%20Almost%20Public%20Private%20Schools.pdf (Date of access: 08.12.2019).
- Bilgili, M. (2011), "Evaluation of Geography Education and Training in Primary and Secondary Schools in France in Terms of Curriculum, Method and Tools", Marmara University Institute of Educational Sciences, PhD thesis, Istanbul.
- Cansu, U. D. (2003), "19. Developmental Education in Japan and Turkey Century ", Ankara University Institute of Social Sciences, Master Thesis. Ankara.
- Center for Education Reform, "California Charter Law",20 Ocak 2004, https://lao.ca.gov/2004/charter_schools/012004_charter_schools.htm (Date of access: 18.12.2019).
- Cohn, E., Geske T. (1989). The Economics of Education. Oxford, Pergamon Press.

- Demirel, O. (2005), *The Art of Teaching*, Ankara, PegemA Publishing.
- Ekinci, A., (2010), "Good Examples from the Japanese Education System to the Turkish Education System", *Milli Eğitim Dergisi*, Fall, Issue 188.
- France Ministry Education National, (2012), "School Education in France, Files on School Education 2012", https://cache.media.eduscol.education.fr/file/dossiers_/07/3/2013_School_Education_in_France_244073.pdf.
- Graddy, K. & Stevens, M. (2005), "The Impact Of School Resources On Student Performance: A Study Of Private Schools In The United Kingdom, *Industrial and Labor Relations Review*", Sage Journals, April 1, Volume: 58 issue: 3.
- Griffin, Noella C. & Wohlstetter P.(2001) "Building a Plane While Flying It: Early Lessons from Developing Charter Schools", *Teachers College Record*, 103, no. 2 (2001).
- Guarino C.M., Galama T., Constant L. & Others,(2009), "Developing a School Finance System for K-12 Reform in Qatar", RAND Corporation, Qatar.
- Guthrie, James W., & Matthew G. Springer,(2007) "Courtroom Alchemy: Adequacy Advocates Turn Guesstimates into Gold." *Education Next*, Winter. v7 n1.
- Hélary L., *Écoles privées hors contrat: six questions pour comprendre le débat*, Ouest-Fransa. Published 21.02.2018, <https://www.ouest-france.fr/education/ecole/ecoles-privées-hors-contrat-six-questions-pour-comprendre-le-debat-5573831> (Date of access: 27.03.2020).
- Hesapçioğlu M. & Çelebi N., (2011), "Educational and Financial Structures of Magnet and Charter Schools", *M.U. Atatürk Faculty of Education Journal of Educational Sciences*, Issue: 33.
- International Bureau of Education (IBE), 2006, *World Data on Education*. 6th edition. Tokyo.
- Ipekyolu Development Agency (2018), *Investment Incentive Guide*, <https://www.ika.org.tr/upload/yayinlar/Yatirim-Tesvik-Rehberi-526439.pdf> (Date of access: 04.12.2019).
- Japanese Private School Law, JPSL(2007), https://elaws.e-gov.go.jp/search/elawsSearch/elaws_search/lsg0500/detail?lawId=324AC0000000270 (Date of access: 27.01.2020).
- Kayhan, N., (2009), "21. Century in Japan Changes in Human Resource Management and Industrial Relations System ", *Communication Workers Union of Turkey Publications*, Ltd. Train Şti., Ankara.
- Kuehn, L.,(1995), "Ten Problems With Charter Schools, BTCF Reseach Report", British Columbia Teachers' Federation.
- Kumbaracıbaşı,O.,Erdoğan S.,(1981).Introduction to Economy,Ankara, Daily News Web Offset Facilities
- Kurul Tural N. (2019), *Education funding*. Ankara, Political Bookstore.
- Law of Georgia on General Education, (2005), Chapter III,Article-23, <http://www.matsne.gov.ge> (Date of access: 19.02.2020).
- Levin, H.M.(1987).(Ed: G. Psacharopoulos)"WorkandEducation".*EconomicsofEducation Research And Studies*. Oxford, Pergamon Press.

- Lohmann, J., (February,2004), "Interdistrict Magnet School Funding, OLR Reseach Report", <https://www.cga.ct.gov/2004/rpt/2004-R-0223.htm> (Date of access: 11.12.2019).
- Mext (2007). Ministry of Education, Culture, Sports, Science and Technology, Japan.
- Machin S., & Wilson J., (2009)"Public and Private Schooling Initiatives in England", (Ed. Rajashri Chakrabarti and Paul E. Peterson), School Choice International, The MIT Press, Massachusetts Institute of Technology, Cambridge, Massachusetts, London, England.
- Ministry of National Education-MONE (2019), Press Release,<https://meb.gov.tr/basin-bulteni/haber/17926/tr> (Date of access:10.02.2020).
- National Charter School-Resource Center, Funding Opportunities, (2018), <https://charterschoolcenter.ed.gov/funding/funding-opportunities> (Date of access: 07.02.2020).
- Nozawa, M., Wing, C., Chaiyasook, S., &Yabu, Y., (2011) "Secondary Education Regional Information Base: Country Profile, Japan", Published by the UNESCO Asia and Pacific Regional Bureau for Education, 20 pp, UNESCO Bangkok, Japonya.
- Official Gazette, 12 Aug 2018, No: 30507, <https://www.resmigazete.gov.tr/> (Date of access: 20.11.2019).
- Organisation of the education system in France, (2010), European Commission Education, Audiovisual & Culture- Executive Agency.
- General Directorate of Private Education Institutions -OOKGM, (2018), Education and Training Support Application E-Guide for Students Studying / Will Study in Private Schools within the scope of Law No. 5580 <https://ookgm.meb.gov.tr/www/egitim-ve-ogretim-destegi-2018-2019/icerik/1295> (Date of access:16.11.2019).
- Palfreyman D. (2003)," Independent Schools and Charitable Status: Legal Meaning, Taxation Advantages, and Potential Removal, Walford G.(Ed.), British Private Schools- Research on Policy and Practice", Woburn Press, University of Oxford, Great Britain London,.
- Patton, M., (2002). Qualitative Research And Evaluation Methods. [http://lst-iiiep.iiiep-unesco.org/cgi-bin/wwwi32.exe/\[in=epidoc1.in\]/?t2000=018602/\(100\).3](http://lst-iiiep.iiiep-unesco.org/cgi-bin/wwwi32.exe/[in=epidoc1.in]/?t2000=018602/(100).3). (Date of access: 24.11.2019).
- Policy and Program Studies Service, Evaluation of Magnet Schools Assistance Program Final Report, (2003), <http://www.ed.gov/rschstat/eval/choice/magneteval/casestudies.pdf> (Date of access: 15.02.2020,s.97).
- Punch, K. F. (2005). Introduction to Social Research-Qualitative and Quantitative Approaches (Translated by: Dursun Bayrak, H. Bader Arslan and Zeynep Akyüz), Political Publishing House, Ankara.
- Ministry of Industry and Technology Support and Incentives / Investment Incentive Systems,<https://www.sanayi.gov.tr/destek-ve-tesvikler/yatirim-tesvik-sistemle>(Date of access: 25.03.2020).
- School Funding System and Equity Research Report -SFSandERR,(2014) Centre for Civil Integration and Inter-Ethnic Relations (CCIIR), Tbilisi.

- Simsek, H. (2009), "Method Problem in Educational History Research", *Journal of Ankara University Faculty of Educational Sciences*, 42 (1).
- T.R. Presidency Strategy and Budget Directorate-CBSBB (2019), "Eleventh Development Plan (2019-2023)", <http://www.sbb.gov.tr/wp-content/uploads/2019/07/OnbirinciKalkinmaPlani.pdf> (Date of access: 09.03.2020).
- US Department of Education (2003),"Evaluation of the Magnet Schools Assistance Program, 1998 Grantees Final Report", <http://www.ed.gov/rschstat/eval/choice/magneteval/finalreport.doc> (Date of access: 20.03.2020).
- Vasconcellos, M., and Bongrand, P.,(2013)," Le système éducatif" Cinquième Édition, La Découverte, Publisher: Editions La Découverte, Paris.
- Verneuil, Y.(2011),"Les accords Lang-Cloupet (1992-1993) : une histoire écrite à l'avance? ",*Histoire de l'éducation*, pp.51-87,s.57Français.
- Walford, G. (2003), "British Private Schools- Research on Policy and Practice", (Ed. Geoffrey Walford), *Muslim Schools in Britain*, Woburn Press, University of Oxford, Great Britain London.
- William E. Thro, (2012), "School Finance",(Ed. William E. Thro), *Should the State Create and Fund Charter Schools That Are Not Subject to the Same Standards and Requirements as Traditional Schools?*, SAGE Publications, Inc. , Christopher Newport University, Washington, United States.